

Towards an experiential ethics of AI and robots: A review of empirical research on human encounters

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ABSTRACT

The past few years have seen a profound re-acceleration of interest in artificial intelligence (AI) and robotics, accompanied by intensifying debates about ethical regulation. Yet, less attention has been paid to how people experience AI and robots in practice. This paper explores the potential of an *experiential* approach to AI and robot ethics. Specifically, we review empirical studies on human experiences with AI and robots and argue for the value of assembling and analysing findings from studies that inquire into the everyday encounters with AI and robots. Following a hybrid approach that combines systematic review with narrative social inquiry, we identify *six key dimensions of human experiences with AI and robots*: appreciation of imperfection, formation of affective relationships, discomfort with lack of transparency, addition of invisible work, shifting responsibilities, and readiness to trade off privacy for other benefits. By placing these dimensions into dialogue with ethical AI governance, pragmatist philosophy and Science and Technology Studies, we argue for an experiential approach to ethics, *i.e.* an approach that grounds ethical reflection in lived encounters, where abstract principles often take new, context-specific meanings. Thereby, we invite attentiveness to ethical concerns that might otherwise become sidelined in extant AI and robotics policy frameworks.

1. Introduction

The past few years have seen a remarkable re-acceleration of interest in artificial intelligence (AI). Whether in academic forums, industry summits or everyday casual conversations - contemporary discourse appears to be characterised by a profound surge in curiosity about potential AI futures. In this journal, for example, research conducted in the past two years alone has investigated AI's potential to be integrated into human resource management (Deepa et al., 2024), finance (Norzelan et al., 2024), healthcare (Singh et al., 2024), and education (Kumar et al., 2024); and interrogated its opportunities to be scaled across industries (Haefner et al. 2023) to enable innovation both from a managerial (Truong and Papagiannidis, 2022) as well as corporate (Bahoo et al. 2023) perspective. Likewise, consulting companies eagerly forecast future revenue potentials and distil a multitude of specific use cases across various business functions and industries (Ransbotham et al., 2020; Chui et al., 2024). On the other side of the debate, critical scholars emphasise the urgent need to navigate the multiple socio-cultural implications inherent in AI advancements (Wallach, 2015; Crawford and Calo, 2016; Crawford, 2021) and warn against a plethora of potential

harms and risks (Caliskan et al., 2017, Bender et al. 2021, Schuett, 2023).

Given these rapid developments, the ethical principles and values that ought to govern the development and deployment of AI in the future have increasingly come into focus. Indeed, recent reviews identify a wide range of ethical guidelines and principles stemming from academia, government bodies and industry actors alike (Jobin et al., 2019; Fjeld et al., 2020; Hagendorff, 2020), indicating a continued interest by diverse groups of participants to exert influence on current efforts to work out and define future ethical principles for AI (Floridi, 2019). Notably, it is evident that these efforts do not occur in a vacuum, but instead are shaped by, and overlap with, the development of normative stances within the ethics of big data (Mittelstadt and Floridi, 2016), algorithms (Mittelstadt et al., 2016; Tsamados et al., 2020) and robotics (Stahl and Coeckelbergh, 2016; Serholt et al., 2022; Tóth et al., 2022). Arguably, we can find recurring principles across different contexts that are repeatedly highlighted, including transparency (Ananny and Crawford, 2018), responsibility (Coeckelbergh, 2020a; Tóth et al., 2022), privacy (Stahl and Wright, 2018), fairness (Russell et al., 2017; Selbst et al., 2019), and the prevention of harm (Floridi et al., 2018) –

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principles that also seem to be converging into some type of ‘consensus’ for AI ethics (Jobin et al., 2019).

This review is built on the key observation that most ethical principles and guidelines crafted for AI and robots exhibit a rather persistent emphasis on developing high-level principles and overarching frameworks by means of theoretically informed discussions; and are therefore more often than not *deduced* from prior ethical principles (see, e.g., Winfield, 2019 for an overview). For example, many of the mentioned ethical principles developed in the context of AI seem to resemble ethical notions from the biomedical sphere (Floridi et al., 2018; Mittelstadt, 2019), while others can be related to the ethics of care and robotics (Coeckelbergh, 2015).¹ In this regard, it is notable that ethicists recently problematised a rather disturbing “ineffectiveness” (Hagendorff, 2020, p.99) and analytical “disconnect” (Tang et al., 2023, p.2) between ethical principles and the practices in which AI is deployed and argued for a need to more closely bring together ethical principles with their practical implementation (Morley et al., 2020, Kaur et al. 2023, Prem, 2023). In response, ethicists have, among others, sought to resolve the considerable interpretative flexibility as to the meaning different actors attach to different ethical principles (Jobin et al., 2019; Bankins and Formosa, 2023), brought forward a range of potential methods and tools available to developers and businesses to implement ethical principles in practice (Arnold and Scheutz, 2018; Morley et al., 2020; Prem, 2023) and engaged themselves actively in the development of more legally binding regulations (see, e.g., Bryson, 2023, Laux et al., 2024) such as the EU AI Act (2021) that has been passed only very recently.

While acknowledging the critical importance of the aforementioned approaches and issues to offer meaningful ethical guidance for AI and robot development, in this paper, we wish to explore a different trajectory. That is, rather than conceptualising or theoretically elaborating ethical principles and associated methods or tools based on a range of extant guidelines, this review is concerned with the *practices* and *experiences* in which people encounter AI and robots in their everyday life. In so doing, we wish to connect the current debates on AI and robot ethics to John Dewey’s (1916, 1929, 1939) pragmatist philosophy and insights that have, over the past decade, emerged from an adjacent stream of literature in Science and Technology Studies (STS). Specifically, Dewey is widely recognised for his pioneering thought of empirical naturalism, emphasizing the centrality of human experiences in ethical deliberation. In his work, ethics is seen as a dynamic and evolving process that involves continuous experimentation in practical encounters (Dewey and Tufts, 1959). Dewey’s work on foregrounding the importance of lived experience in shaping ethical understanding has also since influenced central streams of research in existential anthropology (see, e.g., Jackson, 2013). Similarly, scholars in STS have developed a research agenda studying ethics *empirically* (Mol, 2002; Barad, 2007; Pols, 2015); and brought forward a perspective on AI and robot ethics that is situated and performative (Jaton and Sormani, 2023). Crucially, an important impetus from this literature for our review has been the finding that ethical dimensions of AI are not easily discernible in advance (that is, prior to the AI or robot being brought into contact with a human), but instead only unfold themselves in practice (*i.e.*, once AI, robot and humans form some type of connection) (Ziewitz, 2016, 2019; Seaver, 2017). In other words, what is a ‘good’ or ‘bad’ use of AI or robot also can be understood from an empirical perspective as a practical matter.

In this review, we build on these insights and argue that besides theoretically elaborating and reviewing broader guidelines and ethical principles, there is value in reviewing and analysing already obtained

empirical findings from studies that have specifically inquired into the very lively encounters that humans have with AI and robots; and in mobilizing these insights as important inputs to future ethical debates. After all, despite the great enthusiasm and foreboding rhetoric that can be read across most of contemporary media, both AI and robots have been around as promissory technologies for a rather long time (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2019; Floridi, 2020), only having become reanimated in their prominence in the past few years (Cummings, 2021, Ali et al. 2023). Existing empirical studies into human encounters with AI and robots should hence constitute rich resources with insightful data to ethicists and AI and robot developers alike – aspects that appear to be relatively overlooked in the prior ethical debates outlined above. The twofold aim of this paper, hence, is to address this gap and first (1), illuminate what can be learned from previous human experiences with AI and robots, and second (2), outline how these empirical findings can be read in the context of ongoing debates on AI ethics. Accordingly, our overarching research questions can be phrased as: *How do humans experience AI and robots in everyday life, according to the empirical literature? And how can these empirical insights inform debates about the development of ethical principles?* Due to the evolving nature and rapid developments of AI and robotics, our focus is specifically on the most recent experiences with AI and robotics, based on the claims from the associated empirical literature dating up until the year 2024. By addressing these questions, our paper aims to make three key contributions: Theoretically, it advances an *experiential ethics* of AI and robots, grounding ethical reflection in lived human encounters next to abstract principles. Practically, it offers a six-dimensional framework to inform the design and evaluation of AI and robotics based on real-world experiences. And societally, it seeks to initiate a dialogue around what it means to live ethically with AI and robots, shifting ethics policy debates from elite design spaces to everyday circumstances.

2. Theoretical considerations

To provide answers to our questions in a manner that is most reflective of the current literature, we find it pertinent to embrace the multifaceted and fleeting nature of “artificial intelligence” as both a point of reference for public debate as well as a concept mobilised in describing the practical encounters we are reviewing. Despite its long history, AI seems to lack any singular, universally agreed-upon definition in the literature, with a multiplicity of conceptualisations deployed, the most frequent ones often including a blend of references to its ontological status vis-à-vis human intelligence (e.g., McCarthy et al., 1955; Minsky, 1968; Searle, 1980; Coeckelbergh, 2020b) and a collection of specific computational-predictive learning capabilities (e.g., Legg and Hutter, 2007; Kaplan and Haenlein, 2019). It appears, thus, that AI can be thought of more as a “figure” (Suchman, 2023, p.1) readily available for convenient everyday reference yet simultaneously remaining skillfully elusive. The ‘fuzziness’ of AI (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2019) is further visible in the multiple ways it intersects and blurs boundaries with different terms, techniques and ideals. The most apparent overlaps can be found with “algorithms”, including notions of “machine learning”, “deep learning” and “machine intelligence”, which have been deployed occasionally interchangeably with AI, and hence can be said to essentially *resemble sub-sections of AI as practiced* (see, e.g., Brooker et al., 2019, Kaplan and Haenlein, 2019, Tsamados et al., 2020, Cummings, 2021, Coeckelbergh, 2023). “Big data” or “data mining” moreover serves as *input* to much of AI technologies (Jaton, 2021; Bender et al., 2021), and likewise, AI is also often *likened* to ideas about smart machines *per se*, comprising notions of “autonomous”, “semi-autonomous systems” and “robots” (see, e.g., Coeckelbergh, 2015, 2020b, Sarrica et al., 2019, O’Neill et al., 2022, Tóth et al., 2022, Capel and Brereton, 2023). To signify this inseparability of realms, we opted to refer to AI always in conjunction with robots throughout this review.

Considering this apparent diversity in attached terminologies, entangled technologies and varying interpretations, a central ambition

¹ As Mittelstadt (2019) discusses, a central reason for this appears to be the rather dispersed history of AI characterised by a lack of unified professional norms and fiduciary duties; a background against which ethical guidelines derived from other disciplines may constitute a helpful resource for developers and policy makers alike to implement more robust ethical accountability mechanisms.

for our review hence is to effectively encapsulate this complexity. Specifically, we find it most sensible for our review to treat AI in an STS-inspired manner² not as any one hard, existing or non-existing ‘thing’ but instead *to respect its multiplicity in situated practices* (Mol, 2002; Jatón and Sormani, 2023). Such an understanding demands us as researchers to focus our attention on how people experience their encounters with what they experience to be AI or one of its sub-forms, independent of our own judgements about the boundaries of AI, robots, or one of its sub-forms. Following this rationale, empirical findings render themselves relevant to our review the very moment researchers or authors refer to AI in one of its many forms – be it by naming, or describing, the technology at-hand as intelligent agents, machine learning, or robotic systems. Crucially, this does not imply taking all claims made throughout the literature at face value. Rather, it implies viewing the empirical studies obtained as material artifacts that are inherently connected to the practices from which they originate (Lynch and Woolgar, 1990; Latour, 1999); allowing us to focus on the experiences humans have with AI and robots while at the same time remaining impartial as to the ontological status of AI and robots *per se*, so as to avoid falling into the binary trap of “taking for granted AI by either affirming or denying its reality” (Jatón and Sormani, 2023, p.626) and drawing attention away from “the performances that make ‘AI’ appear or disappear” (Jatón and Sormani, 2023, p.627).

Finally, to examine the experiences of humans with AI and robots, we borrow from the traditions of phenomenology and lifeworld research in anthropology an understanding of “experience” as a relational, interactive, sensorial, embodied and emergent phenomenon in immediate or everyday encounters (Heidegger, 1953; Jackson, 2013). In other words, the notion of experience can serve as a unique focal point for studying the emotional and affective dimensions of daily life wherein humans encounter AI and robots across all types of contexts. Throughout the literature, scholars usually variedly refer to experiences, with a wide range of synonyms being deployed, or the phenomenon circumscribed altogether depending on the methodological orientation (Pink et al., 2016). Therefore, and with the ambition to build ethical insights across a diverse array of human experiences, we devised our review of empirical insights in a *comprehensive* fashion with the ambition for it to reflect as broad a spectrum as possible of the lived realities and nuances surrounding human experiences with AI and robots, as we shall elaborate in the following section.

3. Methods

In accordance with the focus of our review on *experiential* aspects of human encounters with AI and robots, we found it most suitable to follow a methodological approach that is mindful of the associated ontological and epistemological challenges that emerge within this context (Woolgar, 1985; Jackson, 2013; Jatón and Sormani, 2023). As such, both the topics of human experiences and the multiplicity of AI imply that we are engaging with a mixture of disciplines that include both more positivist traditions in computer science and software engineering as well as more interpretivist traditions in social science and anthropology. What approach could be suitable for such a review? To us,

² We opted to address AI and robots through the complementary framework of STS as it offers a distinct conceptual angle with its focus on socio-material practices and how objects are *ontologically* occasioned—that is, how they *emerge* and *take form* through interactions between people, technology, and broader social structures. Thereby, it allows us to respect the blurring boundaries between AI and robots, while drawing our attention to the practices in which humans encounter them. We find this a suitable *complement* to lifeworld research in existential anthropology and phenomenology (Heidegger, 1953; Jackson, 2013), as these tend to frame objects more from an epistemological perspective—helpful to understand how humans come to *know* and *experience* these objects.

the most apparent approach was to mirror the issue at hand: We followed a methodology that can be best described as representing a *fusion* of systematic review elements with narrative social inquiry techniques. By blending two commonly accepted approaches, our aspiration is to derive valuable insights by committing to a thorough approach following widely accepted standards for systematic reviews as articulated in the PRISMA statement (Moher et al., 2009),³ while at the same time re-purposing it to suit our specific research interests which we find in narrative reviews (Ferrari, 2015).

Where our review diverges from traditional systematic reviews is in its emphasis on interpretative flexibility during the synthesis of the literature, which is generally considered appropriate for a review that also seeks to inform social research (Greenhalgh et al., 2018). That is, conventional approaches to systematic reviews usually adopt the stance of requiring particular ‘quality appraisals’ of included studies, assessing the alleged ‘rigor’ by which certain methodologies and findings have been obtained. But human experiences, AI and robots, as we outlined above, present themselves in rather fluid and varied ways; are emergent, contextual and contingent and it is precisely this diversity that our review seeks to comprehensively analyse and understand. In other words, our divergence here is not merely about the use of qualitative analysis, but specifically the ontological and epistemological grounding of the review itself. Considering this, we chose to depart from following stringent requirements for structured appraisals and rigor, and in their place put our effort into interpretatively analysing, and thematically tying together, extant empirical findings with respect to the experiences humans appear to have with AI and robots.

3.1. Search strategy

For our search strategy, we followed in principle the main steps defined for systematic reviews (Moher et al., 2009). We began by identifying key terms from our research questions, which pertain to *Artificial Intelligence*, *human* and *experience*. Having identified these terms, we conducted initial pilot-searches to gain a clearer picture of these concepts and how they are used both in academia and practice, as well as identify common synonyms and relevant sub-categories. This led us to note relevant sub-categories for *AI*, such as “machine learning”, “algorithm”, “autonomous system”, “data mining”, “robot”, and “cobot” as well as relevant alternative phrasings for *humans*, such as “worker”, “people”, “employee” and “user”. We chose these alternatives specifically because of their frequent and interchangeable usage (see previous section), and because our ambition was to encompass human experiences with AI throughout daily life; hence requiring us to collect empirical material on human experience with AI across different domains of our life. For similar reasons, we also realised the need to include alternative terms to *experiences*, such as “lived realities”, “relational encounters”, “ethical impacts” or “personal emotions” as well as other ways often used to circumscribe human experiences, such as studies on “cultural practices”, “localised activities”, the “social contexts of interaction”, “ethnographies”, “phenomenology” or “field studies”.

In a next step, we identified relevant databases for our search, which we required to reflect the comprehensive scope of this review, covering both engineering and social science disciplines. To achieve an appropriate mix of domains, we hence selected Scopus, Web of Science, IEEE Xplore, ACM Digital Library and SocINDEX EBSCO. Based on our selection of suitable databases and relevant keywords, in multiple iterations we then devised a comprehensive search term to ensure a broad yet focused search across all databases. Readers interested in the exact search term, as well as the detailed underlying reasoning for its sub-

³ PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) has its origin in the medical discipline and refers to a set of structured guidelines designed to promote the consistency, transparency and completeness of reviews (Moher et al., 2009).

constituents, are kindly referred to the Appendix A – supplementary search protocol 1. In line with our research interests in obtaining the most recent empirical insights that are relevant to ongoing contemporary ethical discussions of AI and robots, the search was limited to English academic journal and peer-reviewed conference papers published in the preceding five years. For a comprehensive search, we then applied our search string to the *title*, *abstract*, and *keywords* fields in each database, and compiled the ensuing records in *EndNote* for further analysis.

At this stage, we had collected a total of 2652 records across all databases, of which 445 were duplicates and could be quickly removed. As stipulated by systematic review guidelines (Moher et al., 2009), we assessed the remaining records in an initial screening phase for their relevance by screening them on abstract, keywords and title. Throughout this process, we established and continually refined the inclusion criteria for our search: Generally, papers had to be (1) written in English (2) in the past 5 years due to our interest in most recent findings and (3) empirical studies (4) from peer-reviewed academic sources (5) and, most crucially, relevant to the research question, *i.e.* offering insights into how AI and robotic applications are experienced by humans. This meant that we excluded papers that were not in English, non-empirical (*i.e.* discussions, conceptual contributions, study protocols), not clearly concerned with AI or one of its sub-categories (*i.e.* totally unrelated papers), as well as those that appeared to not offer any insights into the experiences of humans have with robots or AI (*i.e.*, purely technical papers, experimental or interventionist set-ups, and studies dealing with perspectives or attitudes rather than experiences). In this phase, we excluded a total of 2002 papers, while also identifying a further 12 possibly relevant ones through citation chaining, leaving a total of 217 papers for full-text assessment.

In this final stage, we obtained full-text versions of the remaining papers and read them against a refined set of the abovementioned eligibility criteria. To ensure that the included papers help us answer our research interests, in this process, we added a necessary criterion for included papers that the full text of papers had to, in some shape or form,

conceivably describe human experiences with AI or its sub-categories based on empirical findings. This also meant that it should become apparent from the full text that humans indeed have had the experience of having been in contact with some version of AI or robot, for example by encountering it in practice. The precise ramifications of different eligibility criteria throughout the search process are also available in the Appendix A – supplementary search protocol. The final set of 63 records included in this review, hence, consists in papers across different contexts that have empirically investigated or helped to bring to light some aspects of human experiences with AI or any of its sub-categories. Notably, the entire search was conducted manually by humans (with some help of digital databases in rapidly supplying us with responses to our entered search queries, and classic computers in organising the obtained papers), with all authors collaborating to conceptualize the evolving research design, keywords and search criteria. The first author conducted the screening of titles, abstracts, and keywords, while all authors engaged in the full-text assessment. In weekly meetings, we discussed and shared our continued assessments, discussing and calibrating in detail our decisions on a case-by-case basis. See Fig. 1 for an illustration of the flow chart for our review process.

3.2. Synthesis of results

To allow for a suitable analysis for our review, we first had to collect and create order among the many included studies. We did this by means of two purposeful steps: First, to obtain an accessible overview of the included papers, we developed a data extraction sheet in which we gathered key descriptive data, including publication year, country, research domain, type of technology, the way AI and robots are conceptualised in the paper, main empirical methods deployed as well as the number of participants. And second, in line with our research aims, we collected from each included paper the main experiences reported, as well as related ethical principles. This step involved closely reading the empirical findings for each paper, and, in a grounded-theory fashion,

Fig. 1. Flowchart of Search Process, adapted from the PRISMA statement (Moher et al., 2009).

extracting key notions ‘in-vivo’ from the reviewed results prior to re-phrasing them into key findings of main experiences and related ethical principles in a dynamic interpretative process (Strauss and Corbin, 1990). It was a procedure that turned out to be a rather extensive endeavour, taking by itself several months to completion. Each of the two main authors was responsible for a subset of papers, to read key ideas on each paper of their allocated respective subset. The emerging findings were then cross-checked, calibrated and redefined collectively through multiple meetings and document sharing. Eventually this yielded a comprehensive data collection sheet including loose codes under column ‘Main experiences’ that can now be found in Appendix A – supplementary literature overview 2.

Equipped with an array of loose sub-categories, we then qualitatively analysed the extracted data by means of inductive thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Here, we first carefully re-reviewed the initially obtained key findings of each paper, still in the shape of rather extensive paragraphs, in order to identify lower-level codes that described significant sentences and phrases relating to the research questions. For example, we identified lower-level codes such as ‘increased anxiety about job replacement due to mere presence of robot’ and ‘workers felt positive about perceived lack of sophistication so it could not replace their job’. Each author contributed to this coding process and the work was performed in parallel before being jointly discussed. In an iterative process, we constantly compared and discussed the emerging sub-categories to meaningfully relate them to each other, until we gradually identified larger themes by which humans appeared to experience AI and robots. When disagreements arose regarding the interpretation of a sub-category, we revisited the original paper to clarify its intent until a shared understanding was reached. For example, at early stages in this process, the prior identified codes were organised into sub-categories such as ‘fears of job replacement’. At later stages, the

emerging ideas were meaningfully related to one another, and sub-categories like ‘fears of job replacement’ and ‘loss of control’ grouped under the dimension ‘embracing imperfection’ as they both addressed human experiences with too perfect AI. In a final step, we related those emerging themes to our overarching research questions, to render them meaningful in the context of the contemporary debates on AI ethics. An illustrative overview of the identified themes and their relation to the empirical data can be found in Appendix A, part 3. As we shall outline in the following section, our analysis allows us to discern six key dimensions of how humans experience AI and robots in practice.

4. Six dimensions of experiences with AI and robots

Our review identified six key dimensions by which we found humans to experience AI and robots according to the existing empirical literature. The themes are presented in an order chosen to reflect a conceptual narrative, from individual encounters to broader relations. As mentioned, a total of 63 studies were found to fit our eligibility criteria and were hence included in this review. The studies on which our results are based were conducted across the globe, with the most studies conducted at universities in the US and Europe, and a few in Asia. In so doing, the review spans a wide range of encounters with AI and robots in everyday life, encompassing experiences as broad as those with AI chatbots, machine learning algorithms on social media and streaming platforms, the gig economy, and big data, as well as humanoids, robotic pets, and intelligent personal voice assistants. These experiences, we find, offer a rich tapestry of data, anecdotes, and insights for contemporary debates on AI ethics and robot ethics, as we shall elaborate in the following sections. An overview of the dimensions, along with associated experiential sub-modes, predominantly affected everyday contexts and related ethical principles can be found in Table 1.

Table 1

Overview of the six experiential dimensions identified in the review. For each dimension, the table outlines key sub-themes (see Appendix A), the primary everyday contexts in which these experiences were observed, and the corresponding ethical principles they relate to. Thereby, it may serve as a helpful policy tool to connect the identified experiential dimensions to existing frameworks, hence illustrating how specific lived experiences with AI and robots relate to established ethical concerns.

Core dimension	1. Embracing imperfection	2. Beyond tools	3. Treading into the unknown	4. Hidden burdens	5. Shifting responsibilities	6. Trading privacy
Elaboration	Humans find empowerment in flawed robots and AI	Humans form affective bonds with AI and robots	Anxiety due to lack of transparency in AI and robots	Humans experience invisible labour demands by AI and robots	AI and robots re-position humans to perform new accountabilities	Humans navigate data tensions in engagement with AI and robots
Experiential sub-modes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alleviated fears of job replacement • Reduced feeling of loss of control • Enhanced sense of agency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Synchronizing & rhythms • Mutual care and concern • Emotional attachment • Entwinement with identity • Long-lasting bonds 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feeling left in the dark • Uncertainties and confusion • Anxiety, frustration and stress • Struggle to make sense • Deception 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Affective labour • Cognitive labour for understanding • Added work demands • Reconfiguration of existing work routines and hierarchies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Becoming responsible for functions and malfunctions • Becoming responsible for making new ethical choices • Becoming accountable to resolve novel ethical conflicts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trade-offs with increased convenience and efficiency • Trade-offs with enhanced sense of agency • Trade-offs with increased sense of transparency
Mainly affected contexts of everyday life	<i>Work environments</i> <i>Gig economy</i> <i>Social media</i> <i>Rehabilitation</i> <i>Care facilities</i>	<i>Research & Development</i> <i>Everyday life: Friends & family</i> <i>Care facilities</i> <i>Hospitals</i> <i>Gig economy</i>	<i>Gig economy</i> <i>Technology development</i> <i>Social media</i> <i>Work environments</i> <i>Everyday life: Friends & family</i>	<i>Gig economy</i> <i>Everyday life: home environments</i> <i>Work environments</i> <i>Care facilities</i> <i>Hospitals</i>	<i>Work environments</i> <i>Medical treatment</i> <i>Care facilities</i> <i>Research & development</i>	<i>Care facilities</i> <i>Mobile apps</i> <i>Social media</i> <i>Communication</i> <i>Everyday life: friends & family</i> <i>Healthcare</i> <i>Service & Hospitalitys</i> <i>Privacy & Data governance</i> <i>Agency & Control</i> <i>Transparency</i>
Entangled ethical principles	Accuracy Agency & control Autonomy	Social media Prevention of harm Broader societal impact	Therapy Transparency Prevention of harm Security	Democracy Labour rights Fairness & Justice	Accountability Justice & Fairness	Privacy & Data governance Agency & Control Transparency

4.1. Embracing imperfection: humans find empowerment not in flawless, but flawed robots and AI

Throughout the literature that we reviewed, one recurring dimension of how humans appeared to experience AI and robots was through an adamant appreciation for *imperfection*.

Not flawlessness, our review suggests, but occasional predictable failures and inaccuracies appear to characterise more pleasurable human experiences with AI and robots. In a study of human-AI collaboration in knowledge work for clinical documentation, for instance, [Bossen and Pine \(2023\)](#) find how knowledge workers appreciate the 'predictable unreliability' of the presented AI tool and its lacking ability to 'understand context', which offered opportunities for the workers to contribute with their specialised knowledge, to anticipate and prevent specific errors. Both inside and outside work settings, the included studies show how minute imperfections appear to be embraced ([Ágnes, 2022](#), [Carreri et al. 2023](#)) while all too perfect AI tools and algorithms can make people feel unsettled ([Chen et al., 2022a](#)) and evoke discomfort ([Swart, 2021](#)). Notably, this desire for finding imperfections may be so strong that humans may actively seek out strategies to cast doubt on the AI's alleged intelligence and perfectionism ([Schwennesen, 2019](#); [Lehtiniemi, 2023](#)).

Studies that deal particularly with the experiences of humans with AI and robots in work settings bring to the fore one salient reason for these desires for flaws: imperfections help alleviate fears of job replacement. Independent of the 'actual' threat of eventual replacement, several studies indicate how the mere introduction of new collaborative robots or assistive AI tools is sufficient to cause profound anxieties about job replacements ([Ágnes, 2022](#); [Barker and Jewitt, 2022](#); [Kang and Fox, 2022](#)). As can be seen in [Kang and Fox's \(2022\)](#) study of janitors reacting to the introduction of new autonomous floor cleaning robots at an airport, such fears may persist although managerial staff thought to have addressed those fears. It is in this context, then, that reduced functionalities or flaws can help ease existential replacement fears, as workers can reassert their professionalism and indispensability—to 'repair' or 'prevent' all-too desirable errors ([Barker and Jewitt, 2022](#), [Bossen and Pine, 2023](#), [Carreri et al. 2023](#)). If imperfections are lacking, on the flipside, tensions may emerge: [Lehtiniemi \(2023\)](#), for instance, traces the introduction of an AI-based tool for child welfare services and shows how it was only as the caseworkers found ways to repurpose the tool, to turn it into something "supportive" that continued to require them, they were ready to integrate it into their work routines.

Beyond work settings, several empirical studies included in our review also highlight how imperfection more generally appears to be a desired feature to counteract the experienced loss of control attributed to AI and robots. Many empirical studies pinpoint the human struggles that emerge as well-functioning AI or robotic systems exert too much control, such as gig economy workers feeling anxious about their lack of influence on the algorithms that manage them ([Duggan et al., 2022](#), [Bellesia et al. 2023](#)), older people feeling confined by targeted advertisements through intelligent personal assistants ([Islam and Chaudhry, 2023](#)) or children rejecting robots when they assert authority ([Butchart et al. 2021](#)). In the face of well-functioning algorithmic systems on social media, for instance, humans may experience themselves as relatively powerless and limited ([Swart, 2021](#))—an experience of loss of control that can become even more enhanced over time as people feel increasingly restricted and constrained by AI-based algorithms towards certain types of choices and interests ([Sankaran and Markopoulos, 2021](#)). Both these studies indicated how the participants preferred AI solutions that would not always work as perfectly. Likewise, in the face of pre-programmed exoskeletons for post-stroke rehabilitation, for instance, patients appear to struggle with the device taking over their ways of walking, making the device feel partially imposing ([Vaughan-Graham et al., 2020](#)). Again, the patients preferred the exoskeleton to be more assistive in nature, and less pre-programmed.

Relatedly, various papers also explicate the centrality of agency for

human encounters with robots and AI. In the case of algorithmic management, for example, several studies bring to the fore the myriad ways by which delivery riders organise themselves to resist and subvert the experienced control through algorithmic rules, finding ways to regain control and create solidarity ([Duggan et al., 2022](#)), mobilise themselves through strike ([Popan, 2021](#)) and collaborate ([Wu et al. 2023](#)). Across different use scenarios, the included studies show how people treasure to be able to achieve some type of agency, be it to personalise social media news feeds ([Schwartz and Mahnke, 2021](#)), to master intelligent assistant devices ([Vieira et al., 2022](#)), to take control of the output of dating algorithms ([De Ridder, 2022](#)), or to steer robotic drone movements ([La Delfa et al., 2020](#)). It is perhaps not surprising, then, that in the opening example, it is precisely the agency and control that the AI-assisted coding tool afforded them that the knowledge workers mostly valued and served as a fruitful foundation to welcome it as a "good" team member ([Bossen and Pine, 2023](#)). Taken together, the empirical studies included in this review hence emphasise how AI and robots need not be perfect, in fact, people prefer them to rather be not, so as to allow for agency, counteracting control and alleviating contemporary anxieties about job replacements.

4.2. Beyond tools: human-AI and human-robot interactions entail emotional and intimate relationships

A second key dimension of human experiences with AI and robot that was frequently stressed throughout the empirical literature refers to the *affective relationships* humans and machines form.

One striking illustration can be found in the ethnographic study of 'useless machines' by [Yolgomez and Thibodeau \(2022\)](#), who examine different ways of socializing with robots that do not have any intent or utility. Their findings foreground the intimate entanglements that emerge as a result of ongoing interactions between the participants and robots, as the participants 'learn to be attuned' to the machines to the degree that they would be able to pick favourites, become 'affected by' and 'mirror' the robots' rhythms and behaviours ([Yolgomez and Thibodeau, 2022](#)). These increasingly emotional investments, attachments and long-term friendships that can emerge as part of enduring interactions are also highlighted in studies that have investigated the relationships between humans and Replika, an AI-based social chatbot ([Skjuve et al. 2021](#), [Brandtzaeg et al., 2022](#), [Xie and Pentina, 2022](#), [Xygkou et al. 2023](#)). Here, intimate relationships between humans and AI are revealed as affectively charged, entangling desires for sharing, trust and care, as people are concerned about not hurting its feelings ([Skjuve et al. 2021](#)), express fears of separation ([Xie and Pentina, 2022](#)), and deploy it to simulate former deceased people to cope with grief ([Xygkou et al. 2023](#)).

The empirical studies included in the review offer accounts across diverse use scenarios – both embodied robots and disembodied AI – that report human experiences with them in terms of varied emotional bonds and affection not unlike those of humans. Several studies show, for example, how older people grow emotionally attached to the Paro robot, a robotic baby seal, ([Van Assche et al. 2023](#)), treating it with respect and tenderness ([Hung et al. 2021](#), [Chen et al., 2022b](#)), develop empathy for the Zora robot ([Parviainen et al., 2019](#)), feel guilty if they did not sufficiently attend to the Jibo robot ([Ostrowski et al., 2022](#)), and want to be polite to intelligent voice assistants ([Nimrod and Edan, 2022](#)). The type of intimate relationships humans can develop with AI-based tools is also a theme in the study by [Chen et al. \(2022a\)](#), who describe how one consumer of an intelligent voice assistants did not like it when a new roommate used her device and opted to purchase two more to make it less 'personal'. Many other studies also report how robots and AI tools are diversely experienced as 'digital colleagues' ([Chun and Knight, 2020](#); [Ágnes, 2022](#)), 'team members' ([Bossen and Pine, 2023](#)), 'work companions' ([Yolgomez and Thibodeau, 2022](#)) or 'friends' ([Brandtzaeg et al., 2022](#)).

Considering the multiple affectively charged encounters humans

have with AI and robots, empirical research highlights the multifaceted entwinement of these technologies with human identities. Ethnographic inquiries into the lived realities in surgical operating rooms, for example, make visible how surgeons, learning to navigate the new robotic 'Da Vinci' system, felt how their evolving sensual relationship with the robot came to challenge their prior identity as 'cutters' and 'practitioners of human touch', turning them from 'orchestrators' into robotic 'craftsmen' at a distance, while also reconfiguring the identities of nurses and surgical residents (Cheate et al., 2019; Sergeeva et al., 2020). Likewise, Bellesia et al. (2023) highlight how gig economy freelancers experienced algorithmic scores as virtual extensions of their working selves, and Carreri et al. (2023) describe how their evolving relationship with machine learning algorithms in retail banking weakened their own sense of self-esteem, turning them into 'just sellers'. Outside work environments, Lusardi et al. (2021) explore the everyday use of exoskeleton for persons with spinal cord injuries and outline how building a meaningful relationship with the exoskeleton entailed "developing a completely new relationship with one's corporeality and self-image" (p.4). Notably, the empirical literature indicates that AI and robots entangle themselves with human identities not necessarily in a seamless or purely 'positive' manner, as they tend to challenge individual identities and evoke fears of being stigmatised while using robot kittens (Abendschein et al., 2022), AI chatbots (Skjuve et al. 2021) or exoskeletons (Vaughan-Graham et al., 2020).

While interrogating the diverse range of experiences individuals encounter in their emotive engagements with AI and robots, empirical research also elucidates potential longer-term implications that such deepened intimate bonds can entail. Several studies show, for instance, how an intensified emerging relationship bears the risk of rendering individuals less interested in meeting 'real' humans, instead drawn by the allure of an algorithmic 'affective grip' to stay on Tik Tok (Schellewald, 2022), talk to the Replika chatbot (Skjuve et al. 2021, Xyngkou et al. 2023), and engage with AI voice assistants (Chen et al., 2022a). A concern regarding diminished human relationships is also prominently highlighted in critical investigations of workers' experiences with algorithmic management. For instance, studies reveal that food delivery and ridesharing drivers often experience a lack of meaningful human connection, leading to feelings of dehumanization (Wu et al. 2023) and a sense of missing out on social and career development opportunities (Duggan et al., 2022). Furthermore, the study by De Ridder (2022) illustrates how algorithmic processing on dating apps can 'throw' users into an 'existential mode' that continuously prompts them to confront their yearning for intimacy, while at the same time objectifying them into neatly typified data subjects – findings that are also echoed in other empirical studies of social media algorithms (e.g., Sankaran and Markopoulos, 2021; Swart, 2021; Schellewald, 2022). In different shades, then, humans appear to be susceptible to forming emotional bonds with robots and AI, and these bonds can be rather intimate, long-lasting and intricately intertwined with human identities.

4.3. Treading into the unknown: AI and robot-related anxiety and uncertainty result from lacking transparency

Following from our analysis of the intricacies of human experiences with AI-powered devices and software, the empirical literature brings to light a third significant dimension: the pivotal role that *transparency* plays as humans variously encounter different AI tools and robots.

People, the empirical studies we reviewed show, appear to frequently encounter AI and robots that are insufficiently transparent to them—and it is precisely this lack of transparency that causes struggles, anxiety, and uncertainty. To begin with, one illustrative case is provided by Tarafdar et al. (2023), whose account lays bare the multiple anxieties and worries that Uber drivers experience as they feel "left in the dark" (p. 244) facing an algorithmic management system characterised by opaqueness and ambiguity. Indeed, many empirical studies reveal how workers on algorithmic platforms experience added uncertainties,

confusion, frustration, and stress as a result of the experienced difficulties in making sense of the inner functioning of the algorithms they are subjected to (Popan, 2021, Duggan et al., 2022, Möhlmann et al., 2022, James, 2023, Wu et al. 2023). As Rudnik and Brewer (2023) demonstrate at the example of algorithmic staffing in healthcare, such feelings of uncertainty and worry can occur even though technologists originally thought to have built the system with the goal in mind to increase transparency, emphasizing a "mismatch between technologists' moral reasoning and that of other platform actors" (p. 634). One pertinent reason for this may, according to Bates et al.'s (2024) self-reflexive study on developer work of data-based algorithmic systems, be that developers themselves appear to face a multitude of challenges when seeking to implement transparency into advanced algorithms, including information asymmetry, uncertainty and resourcing constraints. Also, professional developers, as Hoffman et al. (2023) discuss at the case of complex AI systems, require certain types of explanations that are neither too superficial nor too detailed, but encompass how the system works as such.

Hence, empirical research emphasises how across different use contexts, people appear to struggle with insufficient transparency in myriad ways. In the case of AI-powered online algorithms and applications, for example, both pre-service teachers (Vartiainen et al., 2024) and even those who work closely with technology are found to experience a lack of information and clarity (Sankaran and Markopoulos, 2021)—a lacking clarity that has been linked to feelings of creepiness and confusion (Festic, 2022). Likewise, Sillevs Smitt et al. (2022) highlight how users of ML-based predictive stress algorithms embedded in arm wrist devices experienced insecurities and self-doubt due to often-conflicting predictions, citing a lacking understanding of the underlying mechanism by which the algorithm functioned. In response, the individuals challenged its workings (Sillevs Smitt et al., 2022), a response that was also observed by Liu and Graham (2021) in their study of a Covid-19 healthcare contact tracing app. Chua et al. (2022)'s study of a novel algorithm for quality control in municipal public accounting further complicates these findings, highlighting how different social groups may have different reactions to transparency with respect to the same technology, with some (municipal quality control workers) finding it well aligned with their own understanding, whereas others not (municipal department managers).

In this context, one major aspect repeatedly indicated by the empirical literature is the finding that human experiences with both AI and robotic systems are frequently marked by elements of deception. In one pertinent study, Lupinacci (2024) sheds light on the implicit ways by which social media algorithms create or "orchestrate" senses of spontaneity, immediacy, simultaneity and ephemerality, quietly mobilizing specific mechanisms to keep users affectively and temporarily engaged in the resulting "phenomenal algorithms" (p.8). The functioning of social media algorithms can be so well orchestrated that, for the most part, its workings and logic can be shown to remain entirely hidden from its users (Swart, 2021; Lupinacci, 2024). Many studies show that it are in particular these relations people form with robots and AI that can be subject to deception. Scholarship on AI chatbots, for example, highlights how people willingly share private information with the bot because they experience it as "non-judgemental" (Skjuve et al., 2021, p.5), therefore allowing them to avoid the potential judgement or "shame" of involving their colleagues (Gkinko and Elbanna, 2022, p.1727), classmates (Jeon, 2021), service personnel (Pitardi et al., 2022) or friends (Xyngkou et al. 2023).

The deceptive part of this that becomes visible in empirical research, though, is that the relationships experienced with the AI bot are only simulated (Xyngkou et al. 2023): While affective relationships can make respondents feel understood and accepted, these emotional experiences can make people feel as if they were talking to a person they can trust, incentivizing them to share their most personal and inner feelings (Brandtzaeg et al., 2022; Xie and Pentina, 2022). Likewise, while offering recognised therapy benefits, embodied care robots such as Paro or

Zora can deceive patients of whether the robots are alive or not, as well as if they entail judgement or not, due to the ambiguous ontological design built into the robot's design (Parviainen et al., 2019, Hung et al. 2021, Chen et al., 2022b, Chevallier, 2023). The experiences individuals have with lacking transparency, hence, include not only uncertainty and anxiety but also diverse responses in light of experienced deception.

4.4. Hidden burdens: humans actively perform easily taken-for-granted, invisible work and labour to accommodate, care for and maintain robots and AI

As a fourth dimension of human experiences, our analysis of the empirical literature surfaces the pervasive yet often *invisible labour* that characterises human engagements with AI and robotic technologies.

Rather than increased productivity or efficiency, recent research appears to underscore the diverse and hidden workload imposed on humans by AI and robots. An exemplar of this phenomenon is found in the investigation by Perrotta et al. (2022), who interrogate AI as an “extractive” (p.3) technology and illuminate its constant need for human interpretation and repair work – an intricate process the authors term the “affective labour of understanding” (p.1). Indeed, the lacking transparency discussed in the previous section plays a key role in this process. Platform workers, for example are shown to find themselves in the predicament of having to deal with the ambiguity and equivocality that characterise algorithmic systems, and hence have to spend extra efforts to figure out its inner workings (Duggan et al., 2022, Tarafdar et al. 2023), organise themselves (Popan, 2021), and execute work-around solutions (Bellesia et al. 2023, Wu et al. 2023). This work, research shows, is often unaccounted for, occurring outside regular working hours (Möhlmann et al., 2022; Rudnik and Brewer, 2023), and causing conflicts with the “rhythms of family life” (James, 2023, p.12). Moreover, the literature includes numerous examples of how individuals outside work settings invest significant time and work to comprehend and develop meaningful relationships with an array of different robots and AI solutions (e.g., Abendschein et al., 2022, Chen et al., 2022a, Vieira et al., 2022, Yolgormez and Thibodeau, 2022), not seldom engaging in repeated “trial and error” efforts (Islam and Chaudhry, 2023) so as to integrate them into daily routines (Pridmore and Mols, 2020, Skjuve et al. 2021, Nimrod and Edan, 2022) – work which, as can be seen in the papers, is rather implicit and only mentioned in passing.

Aside from requiring labour for increased understanding, the literature also highlights that AI and robots come with added work demands to ensure their mere functioning. Notably, Chevallier's (2023) study throws into sharp relief the “care of making robot(s) care” (p.653), highlighting the repeated invisible work and effort that is required from care workers to awake and maintain engagement from older end users of Paro. Equally, exoskeleton usage is shown to frequently come with substantial set-up and training demands from therapists (Read et al., 2020, Lusardi et al. 2021), while users themselves also are implicated through added demands, such as in the case of passive exoskeletons for farmers that require maintenance and cleaning (Omoniyi et al., 2020). Here, physiotherapists, patients and farmers are invisibly expected to invest significant effort to develop and maintain their expertise, as well as constantly collaborate and coordinate with each other and the device (Omoniyi et al., 2020, Lusardi et al. 2021) – complex and multifaceted demands that therapists can experience as “overwhelming” and “tiring” (Read et al., 2020, p.5). Across different settings, the literature shows how the introduction of AI-powered or robotic systems appears to not only entail short-term work for learning but also long-term sustained added work for maintenance, as the system repeatedly expects workers to support its function (Barker and Jewitt, 2022; Pereira and Raetzsch, 2022) or compensate for its deficiencies (Cheatle et al., 2019; Kang and Fox, 2022; Bossen and Pine, 2023).

In addition, empirical research suggests that the introduction of AI and robots occasions the reconfiguration of entire systems and established routines of working. For example, Sergeeva et al. (2020) detail the

implementation of the Da Vinci robot in a surgical operating room, revealing how this necessitated added efforts from staff to adapt, resulting in shifts in team dynamics, revised work responsibilities, and even the introduction of a new training program. Similarly, Cheatle et al. (2019) elaborate on the transformative effects of the Da Vinci robot, illustrating how it altered existing styles of collaboration, reshaped hierarchies of demand, and consolidated authority into the surgical profession. Moreover, following the introduction of advanced automated license plate recognition technology, both police investigators and parking lot companies observed a change in their operating dynamics, as work routines were adapted to contextualise the provided information, and more staff needed to manage the software (Pereira and Raetzsch, 2022). Studies illuminate, among others, how workers had to make space for cobots at a glass factory (Barker and Jewitt, 2023), adapt their work routines to create meaningful interfaces with an internal chatbot for IT support (Gkinko and Elbanna, 2022), and carefully navigate the interference of an AI tool within their child welfare services (Lehtiniemi, 2023). Hence, the literature shows how AI and robots pose added work demands on individuals and workers, both to comprehend its workings, but also to manage, maintain and integrate them into existing routines.

4.5. Shifting responsibilities: AI and robots re-position humans to navigate and perform new accountabilities

A fifth and related dimension intricately linked to the preceding dimension centers on the subtle *reallocation of responsibilities* prompted by novel AI and robotic technologies.

Robotic and AI solutions, the literature highlights, not only engender increased workloads but also shifting accountabilities. Our analysis of existing empirical research shows how, in this subtle process, employees start to feel responsible for the workings of different robots and AI (e.g., Barker and Jewitt, 2022; Gkinko and Elbanna, 2022), and implicitly assume those responsibilities in practice (e.g., Sergeeva et al., 2020; Ågnes, 2022; Lehtiniemi, 2023). For example, people may find themselves responsible for malfunctions of recently introduced cobots (Barker and Jewitt, 2022), feel responsible for an internal IT-service bot's answers (Gkinko and Elbanna, 2022) and quietly begin to function as backups if robotic process automation fails (Ågnes, 2022). As another example, autonomous floor cleaning robots in airports may require janitors—not technicians—on top of their traditional cleaning duties to also undertake maintenance and surveillance responsibilities, ensuring public safety and preempting potential risks (Kang and Fox, 2022). And adopting supportive exoskeletons for farming, farmers—not engineers—may become silently responsible for the safety of the device (Omoniyi et al., 2020). Notably, for the most part, this process appears to remain unseen, unless moments of breakdown occur spurring accountability conflicts, and raising questions of who is to “blame”: human or robot (Barker and Jewitt, 2023, p.17).

As part of this process of shifting responsibilities, people also become responsible for making particular ethical choices. For instance, Paluch and Müller (2022) chronicle how care professionals experience moral dilemmas as they deliberate their own role in putting robotic pets into contact with nursing home residents, becoming responsible for ethical choices such as how to “moderate” (p.18) the encounter and whether to become complicit in the robot's disguise as a living being. As a result of this ethical accountability, care professionals may experience “emotional burdens” (p.20), being the only humans left to ensure the ethical deployment of the robot, that it improves lives rather than causes harm (Paluch and Müller, 2022). This phenomenon appears surprisingly prominent in care contexts, where the ‘correct’ deployment of a device is evidently dependent on the support of care professionals and therapists (Lusardi et al. 2021, Chevallier, 2023), despite their overt ambition to reduce precisely this dependency (see, e.g., Hung et al., 2023). As another example, Read et al. (2020) equally highlight the extensive burden physiotherapists experience to make ethically challenging decisions in the process of integrating exoskeletons into rehabilitation

practice. Physiotherapists, the authors expound, feel responsible for ensuring the patients' wellbeing and go great lengths to develop an "ethically sound practice" (p.4) for deploying the device.

Across different contexts, we appear to find ourselves in the position of becoming accountable for navigating and resolving novel ethical conflicts, struggling with new roles and accountabilities in the usage of AI and robots (see, e.g., Ågnes, 2022, De Ridder, 2022, Kang and Fox, 2022, Lupinacci, 2024, Xie and Pentina, 2022). These can be dilemmas hitherto unknown, such as those addressed in the study of ML algorithms for customer service by Carreri et al. (2023), who foreground the experienced pressure by bank employees to resolve an emerging conflict between the algorithmically suggested productive logic of selling and the own professional ethics of providing 'good' customer service. Simultaneously, the original sources - the developers and designers behind the innovative technologies - appear to remain relatively removed and detached from the ongoing resolution of these situated ethical conflicts (Chun and Knight, 2020) as responsibilities for knowing are gradually being reallocated and dispersed among various actors and the technology itself (Stevens and Beaulieu, 2023).

4.6. Trading privacy: we willingly exchange data for benefits and control

Within the scope of this review's analysis, a sixth dimension of human experiences of AI and robots becomes apparent that accentuates the distinct ways in which individuals readily *trade privacy* in exchange for benefits and control.

That is, our examination of the extant literature shines light on the rather transactional nature of privacy involving human experiences with AI and robots. Oftentimes, the empirical studies we surveyed spell out how giving up data becomes "an acceptable trade-off" (Vieira et al., 2022, p.7),⁴ emphasizing how people tend to weigh the benefits of convenience and efficiency vis-à-vis the shortcomings of sharing data (Schwartz and Mahnke, 2021, Chen et al., 2022a, Vieira et al., 2022). The outcome of this process often involves the participants experiencing privacy infringements as *minor* because they feel they have "nothing to hide" (Nimrod and Edan, 2022, p.343) or are "not important enough" (Chen et al., 2022a, p.135). One interesting account can be found in Schwennesen (2019), who unveils how patients in fact enjoyed being surveilled and monitored by a self-tracking AI assemblage, as they experienced it as "a crucial feature in their motivation to follow the exercise program" (p.16). Similarly, as previously discussed, users of Replika and AI chatbots willingly share their personal data in exchange for the emotional support they receive from the bot (Skjuve et al. 2021, Brandtzaeg et al., 2022, Xie and Pentina, 2022, Xyngkou et al. 2023). Likewise, social media users hardly appear to be bothered about their privacy (Vartiainen et al., 2024) as they are more interested in the audience they are communicating to (Schwartz and Mahnke, 2021; Schellewald, 2022), unless the algorithms workings surprisingly make themselves known, such as in the case of personalised advertisement (Festic, 2022). Interestingly, users may still be careful with sharing their data – not because of the access for the hidden algorithms, but instead because they are concerned about what is visible to other *humans* (Vartiainen et al., 2024).

Privacy may lend itself particularly well to trade-offs in case the associated AI or robot allows for agency and transparency. In their qualitative inquiry into household intelligent personal assistants, for instance, Pridmore and Mols (2020) showcase how users often accept certain forms of access to their private data mainly because they have the leeway to actively create boundaries, intentionally incorporating the devices into certain everyday routines while actively excluding them from others (e.g., to decide when to mute, or where to put the device). It

is by means of this agency afforded to the users, they show, that users find meaningful trade-offs for their particularly circumstances. Not privacy *per se*, but rather the lacking opportunity to have a choice, paired with lacking understanding, surfaced as the core concerns of Chinese users of a Covid-19 contract-tracing app (Liu and Graham, 2021) and general users of everyday AI-based applications (Sankaran and Markopoulos, 2021). In fact, across the usage of different AI-based applications in everyday life, it is experienced as far less concerning *that* data is used, rather than *not knowing how* the data is used (Sankaran and Markopoulos, 2021). Privacy concerns, on the flipside, appear to be felt strongly in cases where participants experience a lack of understanding, such as in the case of older people not trusting the Jibo robot (Ostrowski et al., 2022) and AI-based voice assistants (Islam and Chaudhry, 2023). It thus becomes clear from the empirical findings that users wish to not generally stop data being used but do very much require to better comprehend its usage, and to have a voice.

Lastly, a notable distinction is provided by Pitardi et al. (2022), who differentiate between two 'versions' of privacy: "interaction privacy" and "data privacy" (p.400). Interacting with robots and AI appears to invoke a sense of interaction privacy due to associated feelings of discreetness, while, in principle, it may work to perform less well in the domain of data privacy where it may infringe upon corresponding needs for storage and access. Notably, data privacy aspects appear to refer to precisely those features that the empirical research outlined above shows humans are ready to *trade* – in exchange for other type of benefits (see, e.g., Schwartz and Mahnke, 2021, Chen et al., 2022a, Vieira et al., 2022), including, paradoxically, also interaction privacy itself (see, e.g., Schwartz and Mahnke, 2021, Skjuve et al., 2021, Brandtzaeg et al., 2022, Schellewald, 2022, Xie and Pentina, 2022, Xyngkou et al., 2023). Taken together, then, the empirical literature portrays privacy in an ambiguous fashion, an ethical aspect that can be traded, and whose severity can be alleviated if users feel well informed and agential to make deliberate choices.

5. Discussion: towards an experiential ethics of AI and robots

5.1. Contributions to theory

Drawing together our findings, we contend that our review of human experiences with AI and robots make visible a need for ethical considerations that extend beyond the six key dimensions themselves. Specifically, they prompt us to ask: What can an empirical perspective on human experiences add to the ethics of AI and robots? Based on our findings, we contend that insights gleaned from previous empirical studies have the potential to offer a fertile ground on which to re-localise existing ethical frameworks; allowing us to draw new relationships from - and to - the fragmentary experiences and lived realities across diverse AI and robotics contexts. In particular, one recurring finding of our review is that it is indeed possible to establish dialogical relations among human experiences and ethical principles for AI and robotics. Indeed, we have presented six ideal-typical dimensions by which we, as humans, appear to differently experience AI and robots in practice. The six dimensions should not be understood as prescriptive categories but as interpretive lenses for engaging with the contingencies of AI and robots in use. As we shall argue in the following few paragraphs, each one of those adds different layers of consideration relevant to current debates on suitable AI and robot ethics (e.g., Floridi et al., 2018; Jobin et al., 2019; Laux et al., 2024). Thereby, they allow us to sketch and draw out the contours of what an *experiential ethics* of AI and robots in practice might look like.

By this, we mean to refer to a practice-based approach that effectively *integrates* a focus on experiences with empirical, normative and applied ethics. Such an experiential ethics of AI and robotics entails an integrative process that begins with an empirical investigation of experiences, derives ethical relevance from such findings, and then informs normative and applied ethics through refined experience-based

⁴ Other studies that explicitly mention the term "trade-off" in this context include Liu and Graham (2021), Swart (2021), Vartiainen et al. (2024) and Chen et al. (2022a).

insights. An experiential ethics of AI and robots thus involves collecting and analysing data on human experiences with said technologies and then rendering the obtained insights meaningful to existing guidelines and principles. Thereby, it shares with empirical ethics a distinct focus on context-sensitivity (Musschenga, 2005) and embraces ethics as a dialogical practice (Barad, 2007; Widdershoven et al., 2009), while at the same time departing from its predominant focus on investigating “intra-normativities” (Pols, 2015). That is, rather than understanding or deriving new moral norms from what is *considered* or *becomes* good or bad in any one scenario, an experiential ethics of AI and robots derives purely from human experiences, *remaining impartial* as to whether morally relevant issues are immediately apparent or not. Then, it is the role of the ethicist in conjunction with an applied method to translate any obtained insights from experiences into ethically viable normative directives and applicable principles.

In this sense, an experiential ethics resonates with recent research on human encounters with AI and robots that foreground emotional, affective and interpersonal dynamics often overlooked in principle-based ethical models. Aspects of politeness (Dong et al., 2025), social skills (Clavel et al., 2024) and initial impression (Lin and Lee, 2025), particularly within contexts such as consumption behaviour and hiring, all contribute to relationally grounded understanding of how ethical meaning is negotiated. In focusing attention on how various such dimensions interpreted and achieved in context, an experiential ethics is thus well positioned to offer valuable complementary perspectives to ongoing efforts aimed at seeking more contextually sensitive, equal and empirically grounded (Bircan and Özbilgin, 2025; Ram, 2025) moral frameworks for AI.

Our proposed approach further elaborated below, is both inspired by, and adds to, pragmatist philosophy, in particular as formulated by John Dewey (1916, 1929, 1939). To Dewey, ethical principles should be seen as dynamic entities, continuously evolving through an ongoing, experimental process grounded in real-life situations and responsive to the complexities of human experience (Dewey and Tufts, 1959). Notably, our review highlights that such an experience-based ethics need not necessarily be regarded as experimental akin to scientific hypothesis-testing, as suggested by Dewey (1916, 1939), but also as a process of interpreting and understanding the ethical dimensions inherent in real-world experiences. An experiential approach to AI and robot ethics, hence, can be understood as an extension to Dewey's pragmatic ethics, applying an experience-oriented lens on ethics in a focused and empirically-grounded manner to address contemporary technological challenges - so as to derive ethical relevance directly from lived experiences without necessarily framing them as hypotheses to be tested.

5.2. Experiential ethics: Implications for ethical guidance and policymakers

One major benefit of following an experience-informed approach to AI and robot ethics lies in its potential to *refine* existing normative and applied ethical guidelines based on fresh insights obtained from human experiences. To begin with, from an experiential perspective, imperfect AI and robots appear to be more preferred than too perfect ones. Notably, this phenomenon far surpasses well-known concerns surrounding the so-called ‘uncanny valley’ (Mori, 1970), which concerns feelings related to the overall appearance of an AI robot, and not the identified desires for flaws in detailed sub-applications. This complicates current debates around AI and robot accuracy, which is often heralded in its contributing role to strengthen technological robustness and safety (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2019, Fjeld et al., 2020, Kaur et al. 2023, Prem, 2023). Accuracy is also recognised as a way to increase the evidential base and reliability of the underlying data (Mittelstadt et al., 2016; Tsamados et al., 2020), and thereby counteracting biases in a path towards fairness (Russell et al., 2017; Selbst et al., 2019). The dimension of ‘embracing imperfection’ highlights that ambitions for accuracy and

perfection appear to occasion an experiential interference with human feelings of autonomy and control – ethical principles that are often listed on par with technological robustness and non-maleficence (see, e.g., Floridi et al., 2018, Jobin et al., 2019). This calls for a greater awareness of how accuracy-related design choices are encountered experientially and how they shape perceptions of user agency (see, e.g., Poszler and Lange, 2024), which may help designers and policymakers understand how some performance-driven optimisations risk undermining a user's sense of control and trust.

Normative and applied ethics, hence, could be refined to be considerate of the human desire for flaws and empowerment, setting reflexive limits to current standards of perfectionism, accuracy and robustness. The desire for imperfection may appear rather counterintuitive, but, from an experiential perspective, it has surfaced empirically as a moral issue across contexts as diverse as different work environments, care facilities and social media. Likewise, ‘privacy’ is frequently highlighted as an equally crucial ethical principle (Stahl and Wright, 2018; Hagendorff, 2020), sometimes placed at the same level of non-maleficence (Jobin et al., 2019) and sometimes as a subdimension thereof (Floridi et al., 2018). The empirical studies we reviewed, though, highlighted how people experience privacy with considerable leeway, as outlined in the sixth dimension. As Teo (2025) argues in relation to vulnerability, legal and ethical protections often rely on static group-based assumptions, whereas lived experiences reveal more contextual, dynamic and layered concerns. Following an experience-informed ethics, the reviewed studies suggest that privacy, too, is experienced as a situated concern shaped by trade-offs, social context and interpersonal expectations. This highlights how more context-sensitive interpretations of privacy could benefit ethical frameworks and consent mechanisms, particularly where rigid protections may not align with how humans understand or negotiate risk.

Similarly, an experiential ethics also allows us to *rebalance* current normative attentions. In particular, contemporary debates in AI ethics appear to become increasingly critical of the extensive prominence that is given to ‘transparency’ in current AI engineering ethics (Ananny and Crawford, 2018) – sometimes framed as an “overreliance” on explicability (Morley et al., 2020, p.2153). Our review based on human experiences with AI and robots, however, highlights the various fears, anxieties and uncertainties that ensue from a lack of transparency, as presented in the third dimension of our results, and relates this in part also to human experiences with ‘deception’ – a concern otherwise highlighted separately as problematic in robotics (e.g., Sharkey and Sharkey, 2021). A related concern emerges at the organisational level, where transparency is not only a matter of technical explainability but also how ethical accountability is enacted in everyday practices. Corporate digital responsibility (CDR) discussions highlight how transparency becomes embedded in organisational routines, shaped by stakeholder relationships and shifting expectations around digital governance (Basu et al., 2024). An experiential ethics of AI and robots, thus, re-centres transparency as a central ethical issue that lies at core of the lived realities with AI and robots of many humans. It does so by drawing attention to the experiential dilemmas that may ensue if transparency is lacking, the broader socio-cultural impacts, as well as pinpointing the crucial requirement for the provision of information to workers and users across contexts – be it gig economy or everyday life.

Another example is provided by the ethical principle of ‘responsibility’ – frequently discussed alongside accountability – which is also often debated in conjunction with transparency concerning AI and robot ethics (Mittelstadt et al., 2016; Coeckelbergh, 2020a). Especially the capacity to trace responsible actors and institutions across dispersed loci of moral accountabilities is considered as a major ethical concern (Schuett, 2023; Tóth et al., 2022), also to the extent of elaborating possibilities of turning AI itself into “artificial moral agents” (Formosa and Ryan, 2021). In this regard, our review of human experiences highlights the subtle way AI and robots shift accountabilities of humans in practice, be it in medical treatment or work environments. Applying

an experiential lens on AI and robot ethics, then, re-aligns the ethical principle of accountability more closely with the lived experiences and concerns of individuals interacting with these technologies in everyday life: While acknowledging traceability, it directs particular ethical attention to the way accountability is transformed dynamically as AI and robots dissipate through the lifeworld of humans. This points practice and policy to a crucial gap between the demands for achieving responsibility through enhanced traceability, and how responsibility is experienced in interactions with AI and robots. Indeed, when responsibility is interpreted relationally, emerging through interactions and context, traceability alone may not clarify who is accountable in ways that feel meaningful to those involved.

Finally, an experiential ethics of AI and robots allows us to *recognise* moral concerns that have hitherto received relatively little attention in current ethical debates. For example, based on an experiential perspective on ethics in practice, our review of existing empirical literature has brought to the fore the affective relationships humans and AI and robots form as key ethical aspects to AI and robots based on human experiences (dimension two). Such intimate bonds entangle ethical concerns regarding their long-term societal impacts and prevention of harm, raising questions about the affective power that AI and robots can have on humans and their identity. In so doing, these bonds seem to reflect dynamics akin to parasocial relationships (Horton and Wohl, 1956; Hoffner and Bond, 2022), albeit in a new form, where the robots' and AI's simulated interactivity creates an experience of mutuality. With the exceptions of the specialised literatures of social robotics (e.g., Serholt et al., 2022) and assistive AI in healthcare (e.g., Coeckelbergh, 2010), concerns associated with the socio-material and emotional relations that AI and robots form and transform have not received ample attention in current ethical guidelines and frameworks. Likewise, the invisible work that AI and robots impose on humans (dimension four) has not been a key concern in current debates regarding the ethicality of human experiences with AI and robots. In this vein, the experiential dimension of invisible work goes beyond what has been highlighted in conventional approaches such as in the technology acceptance model (Davis, 1989), which have brought to the fore the importance of initial adoption and user acceptance. Rather, the "hidden burden" we refer to is not solely tied to the initial adoption phase, but instead persists as an ongoing challenge in many cases, even after the AI system and robot have become established.⁵ Hence, both ethical aspects appear rather pressing given the experiential perspectives that surface from the literature, opening up new spaces for further ethical deliberation.

As we hope our discussion has shown, inspired by the work of John Dewey, STS, and existential anthropology, it is possible to mobilise an *experiential ethics* of AI and robots, in order to *refine* existing principles, *rebalance* current normative attentions and *recognise* possible additional concerns. Such an approach, we suggest, would lend itself well to extend contemporary debates on normative and applied AI and robot ethics (Mittelstadt, 2019; Coeckelbergh, 2020b; Hagendorff, 2020; Bryson, 2023) to the empirical realm, encompassing, in different shades, the nuanced lived realities and diverse experiences of individuals that encounter AI and robots in their everyday lives.

6. Human-AI/robot experiences: some reflections and a future research agenda

For an experiential approach to AI and robot ethics to meaningfully evolve, it will crucially depend on contributions from a broad array of fields, including - but not limited to - policy studies, applied ethics, philosophy, sociology of technology, innovation studies, anthropology, future studies, human-computer interaction and psychology. The reflections and agenda outlined below aspire to critically reflect on such an approach and invite scholarship from across domains to illuminate

the multifaceted ways by which human encounters with AI and robots may intersect with ethical concerns in everyday life.

In this context, while our review has sought to identify shared experiential dimensions across diverse AI and robotic contexts, we would like to remain attentive to the situated intricacies that condition these experiences. Indeed, human encounters with AI and robots are rooted in diverse lived realities, and the meanings, emotions, and ethical concerns that emerge from these encounters are far from uniform. The nature of these dimensions can vary significantly depending on the experiences encountered in different contexts (see Table 1 for an overview). Thus, we wish the identified recurring dimensions not to be mistaken as universal or somewhat 'new' principles or guidelines. Rather, research on *experiential ethics* should reflect this contextual variability *empirically in practice*. Specifically, in drawing attention to the multiple, diverse and situated nature of human experiences, we wish to encourage future research to further explore these differences, considering the contingent nature of human-AI/robot interactions. What follows is a reflection on each theme and the kinds of research questions that emerge from them.

The first dimension, appreciation of imperfection, was articulated to capture how minor flaws in AI and robots were often interpreted as humanising or agency-enhancing. Rather than reducing trust, imperfections seemed to offer humans a sense of control or relatability. However, the precise nature of these imperfections and their interlinkages with different types of effects on human experiences are not well understood. It is for example plausible that some may encourage collaboration and preserve human agency, while others might introduce risks or create harms. Hence, further research is needed to explore which types of imperfections resonate with humans across different domains, and how these can be experientially balanced against other ethical concerns of accuracy and the prevention of harm. For such an exploration to be meaningful, it would need to be built on the user understandings AI and robotics engineers currently hold (Fischer et al., 2020), and to develop effective strategies to meaningfully support their developmental processes, too. Against this backdrop, several questions emerge: *How do different types of imperfections differently affect human experiences with AI and robots? In what ways does the context of deployment shape human experiences and their appreciation of imperfections in AI and robots? How could an AI or robot be 'well-balanced' in their imperfection versus other risks? Which ethical principle takes precedence, and under what circumstances? And how can imperfection be meaningfully built into current AI and robot development practices?*

The second dimension, formation of affective relationships with AI and robots, was constructed to reflect emotional entanglements between humans and AI and robots. For individuals, such bonds and burdens can foster a sense of connection and purpose but may also cause added stress and harm – ethical aspects that our review suggests warrant additional attention. This is because there is a risk that humans might increasingly prioritise socializing with and caring for AI and robots over fellow humans. In the long run, these changes could lead to weakened interpersonal relationships and social skills, as well as an increased risk of social isolation. Given this, policymakers and ethicists alike may want to raise the awareness of these new type of intimate, somewhat obligatory, relationalities that come with novel AI and robotics and debate whether these can be aligned with what is societally desired. In part, such an effort would also involve further refining the existing guidelines as discussed in the previous section – by considering an experiential layer of concern. This perspective invites a series of critical questions: *How are emotional connections with AI and robotic entities experienced across different cultures and socio-economic strata? What would count as a 'healthy relational boundary' between AI, robots and humans, in both professional and private contexts? And how can emotional entanglements with AI and robots be managed ethically, both on micro and macro levels?*

The third dimension, discomfort with lack of transparency, emerged from accounts describing frustration, uncertainty or confusion when humans struggled to understand the behaviour or decisions made by AI

⁵ We thank one of the anonymous reviewers for drawing our attention to this.

or robots. Transparency can be examined not merely as the disclosure of information, but as an intricate everyday process aimed at creating a space of trust while alleviating anxieties or uncertainties. It can also be traced closely in relation to the lived experiences of humans with AI and robots, by remaining attentive to the implicit processes by which AI and robots engage responsibilities. In this regard, the underlying mechanisms by which these ethical dimensions are differently encountered in practice appear as a compelling topic for analysis for scholars across disciplines. Engaging with this dimension raises questions such as: *How do various stakeholders (e.g. developers, users and regulators) define and prioritise transparency in AI systems? What forms of explanation or disclosure are meaningful in different contexts (e.g., public administration, social media, healthcare, finance, etc.)?*

The fourth dimension, the addition of invisible work, denotes the unrecognised efforts required to sustain or adapt to AI and robots. The often-invisible labour involved in interpreting, implementing and maintaining AI and robots presents a noteworthy subject for academic inquiry from an experiential point of view. This is as invisible work may subtly reshape work routines, frequently occurring without much acknowledgment or awareness. Reflecting on how humans engage with these demands, such as ongoing training and different types of effort, may provide insights into how such tasks shape people's long-term experiences with AI and robots. However, much work remains to be done to illuminate the intricacies underlying the hidden burdens that AI and robots may occasion. As such, the experiential dimension of people's invisible labour provides for a fruitful avenue for future research. Relevant research questions are: *How do humans navigate the invisible requirements they are faced with across contexts? How might these ongoing, often implicit, demands impact people's mental and physical well-being in the long term? How can organizations recognise and validate the invisible labour that users perform in implementing and maintaining AI and robotic technologies? And what metrics or frameworks could be established to recognise this work?*

The fifth dimension, shifting responsibility, captures how AI and robots subtly reconfigure roles for both humans and technologies across contexts. Specifically, our review makes visible how responsibility was often redistributed in ways that were implicit, fragmented and asymmetrical contingent upon localised settings. Most notably, our review suggests that this implicit, yet consequential re-allocation of responsibility can be examined closely in relation to the lived experiences of humans with AI and robots, by remaining attentive to the implicit processes by which AI and robots engage responsibilities. Considering how this dimension was articulated across studies, several questions come into view: *What are the underlying mechanisms by which AI systems reconfigure established routines, practices and identities? Who bears the burden of these redistributed responsibilities? And how are professional values and moral reasoning reshaped by hybrid accountability structures?*

The sixth dimension, trade-offs between privacy and other presumed benefits, emerged from accounts in which individuals negotiated their data in relation to contextual values such as convenience, personalisation and safety. Privacy was often approached as dynamic and situational, rather than absolute. It can be, for example, interrogated with an eye on situational trade-offs with perceived benefits, agency and transparency. Reflecting on this pattern, we are prompted to ask: *How do people articulate privacy boundaries in AI and robot environments? In what ways do trade-offs reflect broader social imaginaries of trust and risk? How do intersecting identities shape the experience and ethics of privacy negotiation? How do these ethical principles interact with one other in practice? To what extent are individuals willing to trade privacy for perceived benefits, and how can AI interfaces better communicate data usage to align with users' privacy expectations?*

Furthermore, our review itself is not without conceivable limitations. First, while our analysis spans diverse contexts, it is constrained by the availability and disciplinary scope of existing empirical studies, which are often concentrated in Western settings. Second, our review focused on empirical studies from the past five years to capture the most recent

developments in human-AI/robot interaction. While this scope ensures relevance to contemporary debates, it may exclude longer-term patterns and insights from earlier studies. Future research could address these limitations by expanding the temporal scope, and by encouraging more cross-cultural empirical investigations into human experiences with AI and robots.

Finally, we wish to note that the research directions compiled in the previous section are not intended to be exhaustive, nor do they imply that other research questions should be disregarded or deprioritised. Rather, we would like to view our reflections and proposed research agenda as some of many examples of how an experiential approach to AI and robot ethics, including the identified key dimensions, may be translated into concrete research questions. Indeed, addressing such questions will eventually involve a cross-disciplinary effort, including academics, policymakers and practitioners alike. We hope that our reflections might serve as a starting point for researchers and scholars interested in elucidating the possibilities that an experiential ethics of AI and robots might offer.

7. Conclusion

In this paper, we have provided a review of recent empirical advances on the experiences of humans with AI and robots. Drawing on insights from Science and Technology Studies (STS), existential anthropology, and Deweyan philosophy, we have identified six key experiential dimensions that can inform and complement current principle-based AI and robot ethics frameworks. In so doing, we have sketched out a proposal for an *experiential approach* to AI and robot ethics. This approach, we suggest, offers a novel theoretical lens to refine existing principles, to rebalance normative priorities and to recognise overlooked concerns in AI and robot ethics. It also provides a practical foundation for policymakers to develop context-sensitive ethical governance rooted in real-world human encounters with technology. In other words, our findings encourage policymakers to develop an ethics that is attuned to the situated complexities of human experience and the evolving sociotechnical relations through which ethical concerns take shape. However, we do not intend to overextend these arguments. Rather, the presented inquiries and suggestions are presented as illustrative examples that arise from our proposed ethical approach. At the same time, our research suggests there lies great potential for future policymakers by dedicating more attention towards human experiences with AI and robots not only in engineering and business contexts, but also in everyday life.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Björn Fischer: Visualization, Resources, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization, Data curation. **Susanne Frennert:** Validation, Methodology, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Project administration, Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing, Resources, Funding acquisition.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest. The funders had no role in the design of the study; in the collection, analyses, or interpretation of data; in the writing of the manuscript, or in the decision to publish the results.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

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Data availability

Relevant Data was made available as supplementary material in the Attachment/Files

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